

End User Performance in Public Office Buildings: A Quantitative Analysis Across Multiple Locations in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

¹Etim, Ekeminiubong, ²Esen, Ubong Okpon, ²Peter, Aniefiok John, ²Akwaowo, Dianabasi Reuben

¹Department of Architecture, University of Uyo, Nigeria

²Department of Architecture, Akwa Ibom Polytechnic Ikot Asurua, Nigeria

Email: ekeminiubongmoses@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study investigated the performance levels of end users in public office buildings, focusing on various Performance Factors (PF) that impacted productivity, health, and overall satisfaction. The research examined PFs such as self-reported unproductivity, sick leave, permission from work, absenteeism, presenteeism, tardiness, fatigue, concentration levels, poor output-to-input ratio, and delivery time. Data was collected through the administration of structured questionnaires across multiple locations, with PFs presented in a negative context to simplify respondent understanding. Performance Factors were categorized into work habits, health-related outcomes, attendance patterns, productivity levels, and delivery efficiency. Each factor was measured using a five-point Likert scale to facilitate quantitative analysis. Mean-weighted value analysis was used to aggregate individual PF scores and derive overall performance scores and rankings across locations. The results revealed significant variability in performance levels, with locations such as Essien Udim demonstrating superior performance, reflected in lower instances of negative PFs. Statistical analysis, including the Kruskal-Wallis test, revealed significant differences in performance across different locations, supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis that there was no variation in performance levels. Locations with better IEQ indicators, such as Essien Udim, exhibited lower levels of absenteeism, fatigue, and other negative PFs, underscoring the impact of IEQ on performance. The study concluded that enhancing IEQ factors—such as ventilation, lighting, thermal comfort, and acoustics—was crucial for improving end-user performance in public office buildings. Recommendations included regular IEQ monitoring, targeted health and comfort programs, employee well-being initiatives, and further research into specific IEQ factors and their relationship with performance outcomes. These measures were expected to boost productivity, reduce absenteeism, and improve overall user satisfaction in public office environments.

Keywords: Performance Factors, Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), Public Office Buildings

Introduction

The performance of end users in public buildings is a multifaceted issue that encompasses various factors influencing their productivity, health, and overall well-being. Public buildings, which include offices, schools, hospitals, and other government facilities, serve a broad range of functions and house diverse groups of people. Therefore, understanding the performance of end users in these settings

requires a holistic approach that considers physical, environmental, and organizational aspects. One critical aspect affecting performance is Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), which includes factors such as air quality, lighting, temperature, and acoustics. Poor IEQ can lead to discomfort, health issues, and reduced productivity (Frontczak and Wargocki, 2011). For instance, inadequate ventilation can cause indoor air pollutants to accumulate, leading to respiratory problems and absenteeism (Wargocki *et al.*, 2000). Similarly, insufficient or excessive lighting can strain the eyes and reduce concentration levels, while inappropriate temperature settings can cause discomfort and affect work efficiency.

The design and layout of public buildings also play a significant role in end-user performance. Well-designed spaces that facilitate easy navigation, provide ergonomic workstations, and offer access to natural light can enhance user satisfaction and productivity (Vischer, 2007). Conversely, poorly designed buildings can lead to frustration, increased stress levels, and decreased performance. For example, cluttered layouts and inadequate signage can make it difficult for users to find their way, leading to wasted time and reduced efficiency (Ulrich *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, the organizational culture and management practices within public buildings impact end-user performance. Supportive management that fosters a positive work environment, encourages communication and provides opportunities for professional development can enhance employee morale and productivity (Cohen and Bailey, 1997). On the other hand, a lack of support, poor communication, and insufficient training can lead to dissatisfaction, decreased motivation, and higher turnover rates (Griffeth *et al.*, 2000).

Health and well-being are also crucial components of end-user performance in public buildings. Regular physical activity, access to healthy food options, and mental health support are essential for maintaining a healthy workforce (Pronk *et al.*, 2004). Buildings that provide amenities such as gyms, healthy cafeterias, and quiet spaces for relaxation can promote a healthy lifestyle and improve overall performance. Conversely, a lack of such amenities can contribute to physical and mental health issues, resulting in decreased productivity and increased absenteeism (Goetzel *et al.*, 2012). Evaluating the performance of end users in any environment involves considering several key performance factors. These factors provide a comprehensive overview of how different aspects of the environment and personal well-being impact overall productivity and effectiveness.

Firstly, self-reported productivity is a subjective measure that reflects how individuals perceive their efficiency and output. This factor is important because it captures personal assessments of work performance, which can be influenced by various environmental and psychological factors (Grawitch *et al.*, 2006). Days of sick leave is another crucial metric, indicating the number of days individuals are absent due to illness. High rates of sick leave can signal underlying health or environmental issues that need to be addressed (Johns, 2010). Absenteeism refers to the frequency and duration of unplanned absences from work or activities. High absenteeism rates can be indicative of a problematic environment or low job satisfaction (Cohen and Golan, 2007). Conversely, presenteeism occurs when individuals are physically present but not fully productive, often due to health-related issues. This factor is significant as it highlights the hidden costs of poor health or an unsupportive environment, where individuals may be present but not operating at full capacity (Hemp, 2004).

Tardiness, or the frequency of arriving late, can also be a key indicator of performance. Frequent tardiness can reflect reduced motivation or dissatisfaction with the environment, impacting overall performance and productivity (Blau, 1994). Fatigue affects concentration, decision-making, and overall performance. Various environmental factors, such as lighting or air quality, can contribute to higher fatigue levels, reducing the ability to work effectively (Åkerstedt *et al.*, 2004). Concentration is crucial for performing tasks efficiently and accurately. Factors like noise levels and air quality play a significant role in maintaining high levels of concentration, with poor conditions leading to distractions and decreased cognitive function (Banbury and Berry, 2005). Output compared to input measures efficiency, assessing how much work is produced relative to the effort and resources invested. This factor helps understand the effectiveness of individuals in their tasks and whether the environment supports or hinders their productivity (Hackman and Oldham, 1976). Finally, delivery time measures

the promptness in completing tasks and meeting deadlines. An effective environment can enhance the ability to work efficiently and meet deadlines, while a poor environment can lead to delays and reduced efficiency (Schroeder *et al.*, 2011). Architects prioritize the performance of end-users because the success and functionality of a building depend on how well it serves its occupants. A key factor is the well-being and comfort of the occupants. Well-designed environments that provide adequate natural light, ventilation, temperature control, and ergonomic spaces can enhance both mental and physical health. Comfortable environments lead to happier, healthier occupants who are likely to perform better in their tasks, directly influencing productivity and efficiency.

User satisfaction and experience are critical measures of a building's success. Buildings designed with the end-user in mind tend to receive positive feedback, leading to higher satisfaction levels. Satisfied users are more likely to have a positive experience, reflecting well on the building's reputation and the architect's professional standing. Additionally, ensuring the building meets functional needs, whether for work, education, healthcare, or leisure, is crucial for minimizing operational issues and enhancing the user experience. Health and safety are fundamental responsibilities of architects. Poor indoor environmental quality (IEQ) can lead to health problems such as respiratory issues, fatigue, and headaches, affecting performance and absenteeism rates. Designing buildings that maintain high IEQ standards is essential for safeguarding occupants' health. Furthermore, the performance of end-users has significant economic implications. Higher productivity, lower absenteeism, and reduced healthcare costs can lead to financial savings for businesses and organizations, making investments in user-centered design economically beneficial.

Sustainability and environmental impact are also critical considerations. Sustainable design can improve IEQ and reduce energy consumption, leading to healthier and more efficient spaces. Architects must also adhere to regulatory and compliance requirements related to accessibility, safety, and environmental performance to avoid legal issues. By focusing on end-user performance, architects can innovate and create competitive designs that stand out in the market, leading to new opportunities and advancements in architectural practices.

User-centred design theory

User-centered design (UCD) theory, introduced by Donald A. Norman in his book "The Design of Everyday Things," emphasizes the importance of prioritizing the requirements, behaviors, and alternatives of end-users throughout the design stages of a structure (Andrew, 2019). This approach underscores the significance of understanding and incorporating the concerns of the intended end-users to create spaces that effectively meet their needs and enhance their satisfaction with the property (Norman, 1988).

According to Vischer (2008), the concept of user-centered theory in the built environment suggests that users' actions within a building are influenced not only by the space they occupy but also by their intentions, attitudes, emotions, expectations, and the social environment. UCD theory recognizes that the success of a building design depends on how well it meets the requirements and expectations of the end-users, rather than the financiers. By involving end-users from the initial stages of the design process, architects and designers can gather valuable insights, concepts, preferences, and responses that inform design choices (Vischer, 2008).

This theory aligns directly with the goal of improving end-user satisfaction. Public buildings are intended to serve diverse individuals and communities, each with unique or personalized requirements and expectations. By using a user-centered approach, architects and designers can create spaces that address these variations in needs (Richie, 2021). According to Richie (2021), the first step in adopting the UCD theory to enhance end-user satisfaction in public office buildings is to conduct thorough end-user research. This involves collecting information about the specific end-user category, cultural background, status, and functional requirements. Understanding these unique characteristics and

requirements enables architects to anticipate challenges and identify features that would improve satisfaction (Richie, 2021).

End-user research is typically conducted through interviews, surveys, and observations (Claire, 2020). Architects and designers engage in in-depth discussions with potential end-users, including citizens, visitors, and staff members, to gain insights into their current experiences and expectations regarding the office building. This information covers their requirements for spatial layout, accessibility, aesthetics, comfort, and functionality (Vischer, 2008).

Once the end-user research is completed, the next step is to integrate the collected ideas into the design process. This means interpreting end-user requirements and preferences into the design blueprint. For instance, if research indicates a preference for natural lighting and ventilation, architects might decide to incorporate ample windows, skylights, and open spaces to enhance overall comfort and satisfaction (Cleo, 2019).

Furthermore, UCD theory emphasizes the iterative nature of the design process. Architects should continuously seek feedback from end-users at every stage of design and construction (Cleo, 2019). By involving end-users in design reviews, models, and mock-ups, architects can evaluate the success of their design choices and make necessary adjustments based on feedback. This iterative approach ensures that the final design aligns with the end-users' requirements and expectations, enhancing satisfaction (Claire, 2020).

In the context of public office buildings in Akwa Ibom State, adopting UCD theory offers several benefits. Firstly, it promotes inclusiveness and accessibility, creating spaces that give end-users a sense of belonging and involvement in the design process. Secondly, UCD theory enhances the functionality and efficiency of public buildings. By understanding the specific tasks to be performed and the requirements to be accommodated, architects can make informed decisions regarding spatial organization, circulation flow, and zoning, resulting in a well-structured layout that supports the building's intended purpose (Olumiyiwa, 2022). Finally, involving end-users in the design process fosters a sense of ownership and pride, leading to increased appreciation and value of the space. Ibanga (2022) describes this as participatory design, which can result in higher satisfaction, positive end-user experiences, and a greater likelihood of end-users maintaining the structure better.

Methods

The study assessed the performance levels of end users in nine public office buildings in Akwa Ibom State. These offices were mostly Local Government Area secretariats. The study focused on various Performance Factors (PF) such as absenteeism, fatigue, self-reported unproductivity, and others. Data were collected through the administration of structured questionnaires to 390 respondents. All participants provided written consent. The PFs were framed negatively to ensure clarity and consistency in responses. These PFs were categorized into work habits, health outcomes, attendance, productivity, and delivery efficiency, and measured using a five-point Likert scale.

To determine significant differences in performance across locations, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed. This non-parametric test analyzed the rank data of performance scores from various locations. Descriptive statistics including mean ranks and standard deviations were calculated,

Results and Discussions

The assessment of the performance level of end users in public office buildings aimed to evaluate various Performance Factors (PF) that directly impact occupants' productivity, health, well-being, and overall satisfaction within these buildings. This section focuses on PF such as Self-reported unproductivity, Days of sick leave, Permission from work, Absenteeism, Presenteeism, Tardiness,

Fatigue, Less concentration, Poor output-to-input ratio, and Poor delivery time. The method used for this assessment involved collecting data from surveys, interviews, and organizational records within the selected public buildings. The PF was presented on the negative in other to allow respondents to easily follow the pattern of the questionnaire as regards the performance variables.

The PF was categorized into specific areas to provide a comprehensive understanding of the end users' experiences and behaviours. These areas encompass work habits, health-related outcomes, attendance patterns, productivity levels, and delivery efficiency. Each factor was measured using a Likert scale or numerical scale, allowing for quantitative analysis of performance levels across different locations. The assessment employed statistical techniques such as mean weighted value analysis to aggregate individual PF and derive an overall performance score and their ranking across the locations. This statistical technique enabled the comparison of performance levels between locations and the identification of areas of strength and areas for improvement within the studied public buildings.

Table I: Performance Level of End Users

Performance Level Ranks	Essien	Uyo	Eket	Ikot	Oron	Uruan	Nsit	Abak	Okobo	Average PI	
		Udim			Ekpene			Ibom			
Days of Sick Leave	1.56	1.65	2.69	2.54	2.07	2.23	2.81	2.73	3.50	2.42	2.58
Fatigue	1.65	2.12	2.31	2.38	3.07	2.38	3.13	2.47	2.56	2.45	2.55
Self-Reported Unproductivity	2.18	2.31	2.13	2.77	2.60	2.31	2.21	3.40	2.19	2.46	2.54
Permission From Work	1.53	1.64	2.94	2.31	3.73	2.59	2.63	2.93	2.75	2.56	2.44
Less Concentration	2.06	1.90	2.25	2.31	2.33	2.92	3.80	2.67	2.93	2.57	2.43
Tardiness	3.06	2.50	2.63	2.23	3.67	3.00	2.44	2.63	2.50	2.74	2.26
Poor Delivery Time	1.31	2.68	2.63	3.54	2.30	2.77	3.06	2.53	4.20	2.78	2.22
Presenteeism	2.06	1.88	2.81	3.15	2.27	3.00	3.25	3.00	3.80	2.80	2.20
Poor output-to-Input ratio	1.80	2.11	2.75	3.38	2.20	2.62	2.87	3.90	3.63	2.81	2.19
Absenteeism	1.63	2.20	2.63	2.54	2.82	3.84	2.90	3.87	3.20	2.85	2.15
Weighted Value	18.84	20.99	25.77	27.15	27.06	27.66	29.10	30.13	31.26	26.44	
Mean weighted Value	1.88	2.10	2.58	2.72	2.71	2.77	2.91	3.01	3.13	2.64	
PI(5 -Average)	3.12	2.90	2.42	2.29	2.29	2.23	2.09	1.99	1.87	2.36	
Ranks	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th		

Source: Researcher (2024).

Table 1. provides a detailed breakdown of performance levels across various PFs in different locations, shedding light on the productivity and efficiency of workers within those areas. Each location was evaluated based on the PF. These PF which are presented in the negative form collectively paint a picture of the overall performance and work habits of employees in each location in the negative state. Examining the data, it showed variability in performance levels across different locations. For instance, Essien Udim had the lowest in most PF such as Days of sick leave, Fatigue, Permission from work, Poor delivery time, Poor output-to-input ratio and Absenteeism. Uyo scored the lowest in Less concentration and Presenteeism while Eket had the lowest in Self-reported unproductivity and Ikot Ekpene had the lowest in Tardiness. In ranking, the most prevailing negative PF was Absenteeism with an average of 2.85, followed closely by Poor output-to-input ratio with an average of 2.81 and next was Presenteeism with an average of 2.80. conversely, the uncommon PF which was ranked first was Days of sick leave with an average of 2.42, closely followed by Fatigue ranking second with an average of 2.45 and the PF ranked third was Self-reported unproductivity with an average of 2.46.

The Performance Index (PI) provides an average measure of performance across all locations for each PF. This allows for comparisons between individual locations and the overall performance trends across the dataset, this helps to identify common trends and areas of strength or weakness. The analysis has it that Essien Udim ranked the best in performance with a PI of 3.12 ranking first, followed by Uyo with a PI of 2.90 ranking second and Eket ranked third with a PI of 2.42. conversely, the least performing location was Okobo with PI of 1.87 ranking eighth, closely followed by Abak with a PI of 1.99 ranking seventh. There were notable consistencies in locations like Ikot Ekpene and Oron both having PI of 2.29. The overall PI across the entire dataset was 2.36.

The result indicated that Essien Udim had the lowest in most PF such as Days of sick leave, Fatigue, Permission from work, Poor delivery time, Poor output-to-input ratio and Absenteeism. For Essien Udim to have exhibited the lowest in the negative PF tends to reflect the provision of IEQ indicators which they obviously had a good level of provision. Same also reflected in the performance index ranking. Recall that Essien Udim ranked the best in performance with the PI of 3.12 ranking first, followed by Uyo with PI of 2.90.

This resonates the study by Mewomo *et al.* (2023) which demonstrated that inadequate IEQ has an impact on occupants' performance (well-being, comfort, convenience and well-being). The importance of the IEQ behavioral and physical environment on occupants' comfort and productivity was also demonstrated by the study. The study also highlighted the four important crucial factors influencing inhabitant well-being, environmental satisfaction, comfort, work productivity in offices and occupant health: These factors are; indoor air quality, thermal comfort and indoor lighting capacity. Occupant comfort directly relates to the physical factors of the indoor environment. Therefore, the better the level of provision of IEQ in the building the better the performance of end users in the building.

In ranking, the most prevailing negative PF was Absenteeism with an average of 2.85, followed closely by Poor output-to-input ratio with an average of 2.81 and next was Presenteeism with an average of 2.80. This confirms the assertion by Kallio *et al.* (2020) which states that poor working environment may lead to breakdown of staff to ill health and having this perceived individual stress posed by work environment discourages workers to shy away from such work environment most especially when it has to do with work places where such staff or workers can stay away from work without being noticed. When this happens, it also tells on the work out-put as well. Hence, the rate at which such environmental degradation poses such threats increases absenteeism rate and that is evidenced in areas where the level of provision of IEQ indicators are not adequate. The average performance index was 2.36, indicating a general negative performance level against a scale of five. This is a reflection of the provision of IEQ in these areas which the staff expressed dissatisfaction with the performance of the building. Understanding the direction of the relationship is crucial. The positive correlation coefficients imply that enhancements in IEQ factors such as ventilation, lighting, thermal

comfort, and acoustics are associated with improvements in performance levels within the examined context. Conversely, deteriorations in IEQ are likely to lead to decreased performance. This underscores the critical role that IEQ play in influencing the effectiveness, productivity, health and well-being of individuals in their work environments. Therefore, the better the level of provision of IEQ in the building the better the performance of end users in the building. The study of Keene *et al.* (2020) supports the idea that infrastructure, resources, and workplace environment significantly impact employee performance. Tailored interventions like workspace upgrades, flexible work arrangements, and employee well-being programs align with recommendations from organizational development literature, aiming to create environments that promote employee productivity and well-being while benefiting the public served by these buildings.

Test for Hypothesis:

The SPSS analysis provided descriptive statistics and the results of a Kruskal-Wallis test aimed at assessing whether there exists a significant difference in the performance of end users in public buildings across various locations which addresses H_0 : There is no significant difference in the level of performance of end users among the selected public office buildings.

Table II: Descriptive Statistics for the performance of end users

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Performance	90	2.3560	.60652	.80	3.69
Location	90	5.0000	2.59645	1.00	9.00

Source: Researcher (2024).

Table II presented a descriptive statistic for performance which indicated a mean of 2.3560, a standard deviation of 0.60652, a minimum performance score of 0.80, and a maximum of 3.69.

Table III: Mean Ranks for the performance of end users

	Locations	N	Mean Rank
Performance	Essien Udim	10	77.40
	Uyo	10	71.25
	Eket	10	46.20
	Oron	10	44.95
	Ikot Ekpene	10	42.35
	Uruan	10	39.05
	Nsit Ibom	10	31.35
	Abak	10	29.15
	Okobo	10	27.80
Total		90	

Source: Researchers’ Analysis (2024).

Table III shows the Kruskal-Wallis test which was employed to analyze the ranks of performance scores across different public office locations. The results of this test include mean ranks for each public office location. The result indicated that Essien Udim exhibited the highest mean rank of 77.40, closely followed by Uyo with 71.25. conversely, Okobo had the lowest mean rank of 27.80, next was Abak with a mean rank of 29.15.

Table IV: Kruskal-Wallis Test

	Performance
Kruskal-Wallis H	36.850
df	8
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Source: Researchers’ Analysis (2024).

Table IV shows the result of the Kruskal-Wallis test which addresses the difference in the level of performance of end users among the selected public office buildings. The Kruskal-Wallis H statistic was calculated to be 36.850 with 8 degrees of freedom, resulting in an asymptotic significance value (Asymp. Sig.) of 0.000.

The results of a Kruskal-Wallis test aimed at assessing whether there exists a significant difference in the performance of end users in public buildings across various locations addresses H_0 : There is no significant difference in the level of performance of end users among the selected public office buildings, was calculated to be 36.850 with 8 degrees of freedom, resulting in an asymptotic significance value (Asymp. Sig.) of 0.000. This significance level indicates a substantial difference in the performance of end users across the diverse public office locations under examination. Based on these statistical findings, it can be asserted that there exists a significant difference in the performance of end users in public office buildings across the various public office locations tested. Hence, calls for a rejection of the null hypothesis. The rejection of the null hypothesis which conversely presents a significant difference in the performance of end users in the tested public buildings is an indication that performance is influenced by location, and according to the attributes and what is obtainable from the building at the respective location. That complements the work of Albuainain *et al.* (2021) which asserts that IEQ affects performance.

Conclusion

The study's assessment of end-user performance in public office buildings revealed significant differences across various locations. Factors such as absenteeism, fatigue, and self-reported unproductivity were prevalent in many areas, indicating a general trend of negative performance impacts. Locations with higher levels of indoor environmental quality (IEQ) indicators, such as Essien Udim, demonstrated better performance outcomes, highlighting the crucial role of a well-maintained work environment in enhancing productivity and well-being. The statistical analysis confirmed that performance variations were significant across different locations, emphasizing the importance of addressing physical and environmental conditions in public buildings.

To address these issues, it is recommended that public office buildings prioritize improvements in IEQ by enhancing ventilation, lighting, thermal comfort, and acoustics. Regular monitoring and maintenance should be implemented to ensure that these factors remain optimal. Tailored interventions based on the specific needs of different locations, such as addressing high absenteeism with targeted health and comfort programs, should be introduced. Additionally, employee well-being programs and ongoing training for employees and facility managers about the impact of IEQ on performance and health are essential. Finally, further research should be conducted to explore the

relationship between specific IEQ factors and performance outcomes in greater detail, refining strategies for improving end-user performance across diverse public buildings.

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